

Moderating Effects of Control Functions on Implicit Cognitive Processes in Health Behavior:
A Meta-Analysis

Ames, S.L., Xie, B., Aragon, J. & Stacy, A.W.

School of Community and Global Health, Claremont Graduate University

Abstract

Objective: Research on dual process interactions involving neurocognitive control functions and implicit associative processes have shown variation in the magnitude of effects. The aim of the proposed meta-analysis was to evaluate moderation effects across a range of health behaviors, with a focus on studies using indirect assessments of implicit processes and neurocognitive, performance measures of control functions validated across multiple lines of basic research.

Methods: A search of the literature from the first paper appearing in 2007 to present was conducted to identify studies addressing this specific interaction with respect to a range of health behaviors.

Results: Findings for effect sizes across 27 interactions with a combined sample size of 4,743 (1,991 adults and 2,752 adolescents) with the specified moderation effect revealed an overall pooled weighted average correlation of .12. Subgroup analyses revealed stronger effect sizes for adults than adolescents, diet/sex behaviors than substances, and inhibition/attentional control than working memory capacity (WMC). Further subgroup analyses revealed larger effects for adults for WMC ($r=.14$) and substances ($r=.15$) than adolescents ($r=.07$ and $.08$, respectively).

Conclusion: The dual process approach to health behavior addressed in this meta-analysis suggests that decisions to engage in a particular health-related behavior result from a synergy between an automatic associative system and an executive control system. In a commonly studied form, this interaction suggests that control functions dampen or block effects of implicit associations on behavior. Findings from this meta-analysis are consistent with research on age-related differences in neurocognitive control functions with implications for health behavior interventions.

Key words: meta-analysis, dual process interaction, health behaviors, control functions, implicit associations

Moderating Effects of Control Functions on Implicit Cognitive Processes in Health Behavior: A Meta-Analysis

Dual process approaches help explain why some individuals are more likely to transition to relatively resistant and potentially life-long unhealthy habits while others are relatively protected. These approaches to understanding health behavior have been advanced through research on implicit associative processes and cognitive control moderators of these processes. Research investigating dual process interactions has shown moderator effects across a range of health behaviors and demonstrated generality in other areas (e.g., problem solving, De Neys, 2006; racial bias; Ito et al., 2015; social behavior; Payne, 2005). The interaction process addressed in this meta-analysis explains health behavior as a dynamic synergy between (1) an implicit or automatic associative system (or set of systems) and (2) executive control/inhibitory systems (cf., Bechara, 2005; Stacy, Ames & Knowlton, 2004; Wiers et al, 2007).

In Kahneman's (2003) compatible decision theory, the automatic, associative system (System 1) is the "*default*" for human decisions governing judgments and guiding behavior, unless control processes (System 2) can be engaged to modulate the effects of these processes. In various forms, this perspective also has been expressed in memory research (e.g., Nelson, 1998; Shiffrin & Schneider, 1977) and social psychological theories (e.g., Devine, 2001; Fazio, 1990; Smith & DeCoster, 2000; Strack & Deutsch, 2004). Further, the functioning of these interacting neural systems and their influence on behavioral regulation has been reinforced through multiple independent lines of research in neuroscience (e.g., Bechara, Noel, & Crone, 2006; Chein & Schneider, 2005; Levy, Stark, & Squire, 2004; Yin & Knowlton, 2006).

Many indirect assessments of association have been implicated in System 1, and previous reviews and meta-analyses have summarized important predictive effects of these associations on health behavior (e.g., Rooke, Hine & Thorsteinsson, 2008). Far less attention has been devoted to reviewing the diversity of studies on health behavior that investigate interactions with System 2. No previous meta-analysis has addressed this interaction. Yet, in dual process accounts of health behavior, it is important to understand

the extent to which one system might affect the operation of the other system, especially across studies and behaviors.

Dual Process Interaction of Focus

Although several different dual process approaches have been advanced in diverse literatures (for review, see Evans, 2008), the dual process and interaction of focus in the current meta-analysis specifies a protective or buffer effect of control processes. In this effect, individuals with better control function are hypothesized to have increased ability to override or dampen effects of associations that promote risky behavior. In other words, those with higher levels of control functions can better regulate associations that might otherwise foster engagement in risky behaviors (e.g., unhealthy diet, unprotected casual sex). Neurocognitive control functions known to show marked individual variability (e.g., Kane & Engle, 2002; Unsworth & Engle, 2007; also see Friese, Hofmann & Schmidt, 2009) may provide one of the explanations why implicit associations in cognition are not always translated into performance of a behavior. For example, when an individual faces a relevant situation (e.g., room with a tray of doughnuts), risky cognitions (spontaneous anticipation of pleasure) may be triggered by the cue and have a potential influence, but control functions can potentially engage countervailing, deliberative control processing that blocks the risky tendency (e.g., consideration of calorie count for the day).

Interacting Processes and Systems

Many different behaviors that tend to be repeated are likely supported by a similar set of neural systems that have been linked to habit development (Yin & Knowlton, 2006). In this approach, associations between cues, outcomes, and behaviors can strengthen with experience and increase in automaticity. With sufficient experience, some associations essentially become part of System 1, in Kahneman's terminology, and can become automatically activated. Beyond general effects of experience with a behavior and habit, experience with *appetitive* health behaviors, related to natural rewards (or neural mimicry of those rewards), is likely to have a more pronounced, or rapid, effect on formation of automaticity. In the case of

these appetitive behaviors, such as those involving sex, drugs or diet, additional neural processes are likely involved (e.g., see Robbins, Ershe & Everitt, 2008; Tang, Fellows, Small & Dagher, 2012). Nonetheless, neural approaches, as well as approaches in other areas (Wood & Neal, 2007) suggest that even rather mundane health behaviors can increase in automaticity over time.

As automaticity develops, an imbalance can occur between control functions (mediated by frontal cortical systems) and some key automatic associative processes (mediated by subcortical systems). The general idea is that associative processes that are reinforced and enhanced by behavior result in neurobiological changes that include the strengthening of motivationally-relevant associations that affect subsequent behavior (e.g., Baler & Volkow, 2006; Everitt & Robbins, 2013). Strong, spontaneously acting associations based on experience can bias behavior without awareness or recall of previous experience. A biasing effect on behavior is consistent with research in social psychology revealing such effects (for summary, Payne & Gawronski, 2010) and with applications of these processes to appetitive behaviors (Stacy & Wiers, 2010).

Although automatic associative processes can likely become strong influences on health behaviors, sometimes overriding intentional control (c.f., Bechara et al., 2006; White, 1996), there are control processes such as working memory, executive attention, decision making, and inhibitory control that may frequently intervene in spontaneously activated impulses. Individual variability in these control processes has led researchers in health to investigate this control through the study of the moderator (interaction) effect of focus in this article.

Measurement Strategies Used to Index Associative Processes and Control Functions

The focus of the present meta-analysis is on research that evaluated interaction effects for health behaviors using indirect assessments of implicit associative processes and neurocognitive performance paradigms of regulatory functions, validated across multiple levels of analysis including cognitive, behavioral and neural levels. Refined neurocognitive performance paradigms have enabled investigation of

moderating effects of specific control functions without involvement of self-report assessments. Several measurement strategies used to examine dual process interaction effects are reviewed below.

Indirect Assessment of Associative Processes

Indirect assessments of implicit processes have been used for decades and have contributed to many theories in basic and applied research that are diverse in architecture but nevertheless converge on the fundamental importance of associations in memory (see Stacy & Wiers, 2006). As described below, several indirect tests have been adapted to evaluate different facets of associative processes in health behaviors (for reviews, Ames, Franken & Coronges, 2006; Sheeran, Gollwitzer & Bargh, 2013).

Reaction time paradigms of associative strength. Reaction time paradigms assess facilitation of task performance through rate of processing of information. The basic assumption is that past learning experiences can be represented by the ease of information processing of associated concepts as measured by response latency.

Categorization paradigms. Commonly used reaction time tests of association in memory are Implicit Association Tests (IAT; Greenwald, McGhee, & Schwartz, 1998) and a variation of the original IAT, the Single Category-IAT (SC-IAT; Karpinski & Steinman; 2006). These tasks provide a relative measure of associative strength between concepts by measuring reaction times during categorization. The mapping of a response key to target categories is switched in different within-subject conditions to assess relative association strength (see Greenwald et al., 1998). Reaction time on task trials is expected to be faster when individuals are categorizing strongly associated concepts that share a response key (i.e. compatible trials). Reaction time is slower during task trials when individuals categorize concepts they do not typically associate that share a response key (i.e., incompatible trials). Incompatible trials require more effortful processing of information. Differences in response latencies are scored according to algorithms described by Greenwald, Nosek & Banaji (2003) and Glashouwer, Smulders, deJong, Roefs, & Wiers (2013). Higher scores reflect a greater difference between incompatible and compatible trial scores indicative of greater

implicit bias. Neural investigation of IATs using alcohol or marijuana-related concepts as stimuli has shown engagement of striatal circuitry consistent with ease of processing during compatible trials among individuals with higher levels of substance use, and engagement of prefrontal systems consistent with more effortful processing of information on incompatible trials (see Ames et al., 2013; Ames et al., 2014). The IAT has widespread support as a predictive measure (for review, Greenwald, Poehlman, Uhlmann & Banaji, 2009), with considerable evidence for construct validity (Nosek, Greenwald & Banaji, 2005, 2007).

Approach bias paradigms. Alternative reaction time paradigms that simulate approach tendencies are the *Stimulus-Response Compatibility Task* (SRC; Fitts & Seeger, 1953; Field, Kiernan, Eastwood & Child, 2008) and the *Approach-Avoidance Task* (AAT; Rinck & Becker, 2007; Wiers, Rinck, Dicus & Van den Wildenberg, 2009). With respect to behavior, these tasks tap individual differences in responses to positive and negative learned associations with stimuli. Learned associations as a result of past experiences affect response bias such that positive outcomes or liking of stimuli, for example, can elicit a relatively rapid approach tendency and negative outcomes associated with stimuli can elicit an avoidance tendency. On the SRC task, individuals move a virtual manikin toward stimuli (approach) or away from stimuli (avoid) as quickly and accurately as possible. A stimulus–response compatibility effect is influenced by the degree of congruency with respect to response tendencies an individual has with the presented stimuli. For instance, a heavy drinker is expected to have a shorter response latency between exposure to alcohol images and response time to approach a target while avoiding non-alcohol-related images (compatible trials), and longer response latency between exposure to alcohol images and response time to avoid a target image while approaching non-alcohol related images (incompatible trials). Similarly, on the AAT individuals quickly respond to images viewed on a computer screen but use a joystick (or keyboard) to move toward or pull away from the projected object while attending to some irrelevant dimension of the image (e.g., object shape). For instance, individuals may be instructed to pull an image toward them when they view a vertical rectangle and push it away (or not respond) when it is horizontal,

regardless of the stimuli in the image (e.g., soda vs. water). When the joystick is pulled toward oneself, the image on the screen zooms in to appear larger, and when pushed away, the image shrinks. On both tasks, difference scores between incongruent and congruent conditions in mean reaction time serve as indicators of approach bias, with higher scores indicative of greater approach bias. Neural imaging has shown increased activity of the nucleus accumbens (implicated in reward learning) and the medial prefrontal cortex (implicated in learned associations and decision making; Euston Gruber & McNaughton, 2012) during alcohol approach trials on an AAT among alcohol dependent individuals (Wiers et al., 2014).

Attentional bias paradigms. Attentional bias is another index of associative processes that can occur without intention and is affected by the salience of cues or stimuli (Posner & Snyder, 2004; for relevant reviews, see Franken, 2003; also Field & Cox, 2008). As a result of prior experiences, conditioned cues predictive of behavior (i.e., learned associations) can capture attention relatively rapidly and unintentionally. This biasing effect is directed towards cues that predict reward or approach, as well as cues that predict or elicit avoidance. One index of attentional bias is a computer-based *Visual Dot Probe* (VDP; MacLeod, Mathews & Tata, 1986). With this task individuals react faster to a probe that immediately appears on a computer screen in a location that was previously attended to than to a probe that appears in a location that was not previously attended to. With respect to behavior, individuals are expected to react faster to probes that replace words or images associated with a specific behavior in which they have engaged than to control or neutral stimuli because of selective attention to associated cues (e.g., alcohol vs. soda images; see Pieters et al., 2014).

Indirect tests of word production. Several word production methods used in health research also have been used extensively in basic research on memory, semantic processes, and neuroscience, revealing multiple-lines of evidence for widespread utility. In cognitive science, where definitions of implicit cognition first arose in the form of implicit memory (Graf & Schacter, 1985), these measures have been used to infer implicit or non-declarative processes directly in relevant experimental paradigms (Levy et al.,

2004; Nelson & Goodmon, 2002; Seger, Rabin, Desmond, & Gabrieli, 1999; Shimamura & Squire, 1984; Vaidya, Gabrieli, Keane, & Monti, 1995). They also have been used regularly to infer key association parameters (such as association strength, density, or set size) usually considered to operate spontaneously, with noteworthy effects when the parameters are implemented (Hutchison, Balota, Cortese, & Watson, 2008; Nelson, Goodmon, & Akirmak, 2007; Roediger, Watson, McDermott, & Gallo, 2001). In either case, the experimental results have often led to the conclusion that the effects of association involve implicit or automatic processes (Hutchison et al., 2008; Nelson, McKinney, Gee, & Janczura, 1998; Roediger et al., 2001). In the domain of word production, the best evidence for implicating implicit processes and for derivation of association parameters comes from methods that use indirect instructions. That is, the instructions do not mention the target of inquiry or require deliberate or conscious recollection of a previous event. A simple difference in indirect versus direct instructional sets in word production have led to fundamental findings supporting differences in the neural systems supporting different forms of memory (Levy et al., 2004; Schacter, 1985; Shimamura & Squire, 1984; Vaidya et al., 1995).

Word production paradigms. Methods most aligned with work in cognitive neuroscience and cognitive psychology have either used *free word association* or a type of controlled association procedure termed *verb generation*. Free word association simply provides a word or other cue and asks for the first word that comes to mind (top of mind instructions). Verb generation also uses top of mind, indirect instructions but asks for the first action or behavior that comes to mind (Karunanayaka et al., 2010; Martin & Cheng, 2006). Studies were included in this category if they: a) used indirect instructions; b) encouraged top of mind responses either in the instructions or through other study procedures; c) used some form of word production or completion (typed or written response); and d) used a procedure that reasonably assessed an association in memory with a provided cue (e.g., word, phrase).

Other indirect tests of association. The *Word-Sentence Association Paradigm* (Beard & Amir, 2009) was adapted by Salemink et al. (2014) to assess memory associations indexed as an interpretative

bias for positive and negative situations related to behavior (i.e., alcohol use). This task requires individuals make decisions about whether or not a word or action related to a behavior (or neutral word/action not related to the behavior) is related to a succeeding ambiguous sentence. Individuals first view a fixation cross, then a word for a brief duration (e.g., 500 milliseconds) followed by an ambiguous sentence. They indicate whether or not the sentence is related to the just seen word. The sentences presented by Salemink et al. (2013) were positive, negative, or neutral situations. Primes were either alcohol-related or not. Interpretative bias effects were calculated (by subtraction) based on whether or not the response was related to the behavior (e.g., alcohol related or not). Reaction time can also be assessed in the evaluation of relatedness decisions with the WASP (Beard & Amir, 2009).

Neurocognitive Function Paradigms as Moderators of Implicit Associations

The measures of neurocognitive control evaluated in this meta-analysis are those that have some degree of multi-method support, preferably across multiple levels of evidence (e.g., behavioral, neural, clinical) and commonly involve the assessment of task performance aligned with a specific function. Included in the meta-analysis are four classes of control functions: 1) working memory capacity, 2) attentional control, 3) response inhibition, and 4) decision making (for review of functions, see Hoffman, Schmeichel, & Baddeley, 2012; Jurado & Rosselli, 2007). Survey measures of adaptive functions, such as self-reported control or impulsivity, are not addressed in this meta-analysis because the range of these measures is vast and in some cases the measures may constitute a self-reflection of performance rather than functioning per se. There is also considerably more multi-level evidence for performance measures than self-report assessments. Although there are quite useful survey measures related to control functions, some restriction had to be applied given the wide scope of survey measures.

Working memory capacity (WMC). Working memory allows for engagement in goal relevant processing of information and the inhibition of goal irrelevant information. Good working memory ability helps individuals keep competing considerations “online,” (Kane & Engle, 2002) even when faced with

other demands on cognitive resources or interference. Without good working memory, multiple considerations are not as likely to be kept active or “on mind” for decisions and memory retrieval is less effective (DeNeys, Schaeken, & d'Ydewalle, 2005a,b; Kane & Engle, 2000); therefore, a smaller subset of learned effects (the most spontaneously activated ones) are available to influence behavior. In general, different span tasks are used to index WMC (see Conway, et al., 2005). A commonly used span task is the *Automated Operation Span Task* (OSPAN; Unsworth et al., 2005) and close variations, which measure executive control of attention under interference. The OSPAN has been validated in cognitive science laboratories (Engle; 2002; 2010; Engle, Tuholski, Laughlin, & Conway, 1999). This task measures capacity to learn and maintain information in an active state in the presence of interference and tests the ability to control attention (Kane & Engle, 2002). For example, individuals are instructed to remember a series of 3 to 7 letters presented sequentially on a computer and then solve simple math problems and indicate if an answer to a problem is true or false (e.g., $8/2+6=10$). Math problems serve as distracters requiring control of attention while maintaining letter sequences in short-term memory. A larger number of letters recalled in proper sequence is indicative of higher WM capacity. WM is strongly linked to the functioning of the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and related circuits (Kane & Engle, 2002).

A computerized version of the *Self-Ordered Pointing Task* (SOPT) has also been used to index WMC with adolescent populations (Peterson et al., 2002). Although this task was developed to assess executive abilities of planning and organization, good performance requires higher levels of WMC (Petrides, Alivisatos, Evans & Meyers, 1993; Ross, Hanouskova, Giarla, Calhoun, & Tucker, 2007), and task performance is associated with neural activity in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (Petrides et al., 1993). On this task, individuals select an image from matrices of 12 images across a number of trials. Images randomly change location on the screen on each trial. Clicking on the same image on two different trials is considered an error. The correct number of responses is summed, with higher scores indicative of better WMC.

Attentional control (AC). A task used by some investigators to tap executive control of attention is the Stroop task (Stroop, 1935; for review, see MacLeod, 1991). This task is used to capture attentional control under interference. On this task, performance impairment in the presence of distractors provides an indicator of attentional control. Because brain regions found to correlate with task activity include the lateral prefrontal cortex (Bush, Luu, & Posner, 2000; MacDonald, Cohen, Stenger, & Carter, 2000) and the anterior cingulate cortex, it is classified here as a control function task (see Banich et al., 2000; Milham, Banich, Claus & Cohen, 2003; also see Galer et al., 2015), although versions of this task are believed to index attentional bias, a facet of automatic associative processing (see Sheeran et al., 2013). In a typical Stroop task key concept-related words and neutral words are presented in different colors and the individual names the color of the word as quickly as possible while ignoring word meaning. Various adapted Stroops have included, for example, congruent trials where word meaning and color are the same, incongruent trials where word meaning and color are different (e.g., Houben & Wiers, 2009), and incongruent and neutral trials where meaningless strings of letters are presented (Woud et al., 2013). Level of attentional control is assessed by subtracting average reaction times on congruent trials from average reaction time on incongruent trials. Higher scores are indicative of a greater Stroop interference effect or poorer attentional control.

A hybrid task of executive control of attention is the *Attention Network Task (ANT)* developed by Fan and Posner (Fan et al., 2002) to tap three aspects of the attention network, including orienting, alerting, and executive attention. On this task, individuals are instructed to rapidly and accurately respond to target stimuli presented on a computer screen while attending to a fixation point in the center of the screen. Warning cues oriented at different locations on the computer screen signal an upcoming target (a central arrow). The central arrow is then flanked on both sides by arrows either pointing in the same direction (congruent condition) or opposite direction (incongruent condition), or flanked by straight lines (neutral condition, as in van Hemel-Ruiter et al., 2015). Individuals are instructed to press a response button that is

consistent with the observed condition. Executive control can be indexed by subtracting average reaction times for all congruent flanking conditions from incongruent flanking conditions across all cue types, with higher scores indicative of weaker control functions. Differences in reaction time for cue conditions can be calculated to provide alerting and orienting effects.

Response inhibition (RI). Inhibitory functioning reflects the ability to actively stop or override a pre-potent/automatic behavioral response after it has been triggered (Logan, 1997). Inhibitory processes are relevant primarily when there is a need for inhibition of a pre-potent response tendency or impulse and these tendencies do not surface continuously but instead are activated primarily by antecedent cues (Wood & Neal, 2007). Individuals with weakened or overwhelmed regulatory control functions in prefrontal systems have a tendency to act more impulsively. Various tasks have been used to assess aspects of response inhibition or control functions. A commonly used task that taps basic inhibitory processes is the *Stop-Signal task* (SSRT; Logan, 1994). Responses to the SSRT correlate with activity in the ventral regions of the prefrontal cortex (Chambers et al., 2006). This task measures the latency of the act of control (or speed of inhibition) with the stop-signal reaction time, indicative of the ability to stop a planned or ongoing thought and action. On this task, individuals react to stimuli presented on a computer screen as quickly as possible without making mistakes. Individuals press a response key if a stimulus represents a “go” signal. A “stop” signal intermittently appears at various delays following the onset of a “go” signal, requiring one to inhibit a response. The task has convergent, discriminant, and predictive validity (Nichols & Waschbusch, 2004). An alternative to the SSRT is the *Go/No-Go task*, another valid test used to assess suppression of pre-potent behavioral responses (Aron & Poldrack, 2005). On this task, individuals also react as rapidly as possible to “go” stimuli on a computer screen (e.g., press a key in response to various stimuli, for instance the letters K,L,N,P) and withhold a response to “no-go” stimuli by inhibiting the response to press a key (e.g., inhibit a response to the letter X), without making mistakes (for a cued version, see Fillmore, Kelly & Martin, 2005; for review of neural systems, see Simmonds, Pekar & Mostofsky, 2008; Aron, Robbins &

Holdback, 2004). A higher number of responses to no-go stimuli indicates problems with impulsivity and is a measure of response inhibition failure.

Decision making (DM). Also relevant to behavioral regulation is adequate decision making (Bechara, 2005). Decision making captures neural functions that are distinguishable from inhibition and working memory capacity (see Toplak, Sorge, Benoit, West & Stanovich, 2010). One form of decision making that reflects an integration of both cognitive and affective systems (an index of a “hot” executive function, see Bechara, 2004), and the ability to more optimally weigh short-term gains against long-term losses or probable outcomes of an action, can be assessed with the *Iowa Gambling Task (IGT)* (Bechara, Damasio, Damasio, & Anderson, 1994). The IGT is a neurocognitive task used to simulate real-life decision making by taxing aspects of decision making guided by affect and emotions. Spontaneous associations promoting a risky behavior known to have a short-term benefit (feeling good) but long-term negative consequences should have less impact in those scoring higher on this decision function. Imaging studies link IGT performance to neural activity of the amygdala and ventromedial prefrontal cortex (Bechara, Damasio, & Tranel, 1998; Bechara, Tranel & Damasio, 2000), the medial prefrontal cortex, nucleus accumbens (Fukui, Murai, Fukuyama, Hayashi & Hanakawa, 2005) and medial frontal gyrus, orbitofrontal cortex, and the insula (Lawrence, Jollant, O’Daly, Zelaya & Phillips, 2009). On the computer, participants choose cards from “good and bad” decks, making choices about future consequences based on reward/punishment contingencies. Higher decision performance involving risky choice allows individuals to more optimally weigh short-term gains against long-term losses (Bechara, 2005).

A variation of the IGT and an index of impulsive decision making is delayed discounting. In general, *Delayed Discounting tasks (DD)* (for computerized versions, see Du, Green, Myerson 2002; Epstein, et al. 2003; Robles & Vargas, 2008; for neural regions, see McClure, Laibson, Loewenstein & Cohen, 2004) involve decision trials in which individuals make choices about rewards based on the amount or magnitude of the reward (e.g., monetary rewards) and timing of the reward (immediate vs. delayed).

Decision trials are varied but the ability to delay rewards larger in value (e.g., larger monetary amounts) is indicative of greater control. The inability to delay and chose immediate but smaller rewards is indicative of higher levels of impulsivity.

Methods

Inclusion Criteria for Studies in this Review

This meta-analysis focused on studies using indirect assessments of associative processes and neurocognitive, performance measures of control functions. In addition, all outcomes of the studies included in the analyses had to be a health behavior as commonly defined, that is, a behavior known to have fairly direct consequences to physical health. A search of the literature from the first paper appearing in 2007 to present was conducted. Two researchers independently searched PubMed, PsycINFO, and Google Scholar to identify studies addressing this specific interaction with respect to traditional health behaviors. Further, contact with authors of papers was made to acquire any submitted or in-press studies. Only papers that included both an indirect test of association and a neurocognitive, performance test of cognitive function were included in the meta-analysis of moderation effects. Search terms included combinations of the following terms: dual process, interaction(s), moderator effect(s), moderation, implicit cognition, implicit associations, implicit measures, memory associations, associative processes, automatic processes, approach tendencies, attentional bias, indirect tests of association, and executive functioning, working memory capacity, self-regulation, control functions, neurocognitive tasks, attentional control, inhibitory control, response inhibition, decision making, and health behaviors such as alcohol, drinking, diet, eating, smoking, sex, and drug use. In addition, we searched for seat belt use, sun safety, physical activity/sedentary behavior, exercise, medication adherence/compliance, cancer screening behavior, and dental care. Although a few studies were found that used a dual process approach for these later searches, only self-report measures were used or there was no use of performance measures of executive control (e.g., Cheval, Sarrazin & Pelletier, 2014; Pressau et al., 2014).

Important studies that may have tested an interaction but were not included in the analyses were as follows: 1) studies with an intervention (e.g. Houben, Wiers & Jansen, 2011), 2) studies that used self-report measures to assess control functions (e.g., Friese & Hoffman, 2009; Friese, Hofmann, & Wänke, 2008; Hofmann, Rauch & Gawronski, 2007; Lindgren, Neighbors, Westgate & Salemink, 2014), and 3) studies that defined the moderator variable as a binary category to test interactions (e.g, Peeters et al., 2013) since all other studies tested continuous variable interactions. One study was excluded from the analyses because it was the only study that tested an interaction with a clinical inpatient population (Woud et al., 2013). All other studies evaluated moderator effects in general or at-risk populations.

Classification for Meta-analyses

1. Aggregate moderation effects. Overall, analyses included all indirect tests of association and neurocognitive control paradigms. The assessments of implicit associative processes described above and included in our analyses were reaction time tasks of categorization (IAT, SC-IAT), approach bias (AAT, SRC), attentional bias (VDP), indirect word production (free association tasks, verb generation tasks), and other indirect tests of association (WSAP). The neurocognitive function performance tasks included were indices of working memory capacity (OSPAN, SOPT), attentional control (Stroop, ANT), response inhibition (SSRT, Go/No-Go), and decision-making (IGT, DD).

2. Effects by moderators. The neurocognitive performance tasks were stratified to evaluate the overall magnitude of effect by function. Moderators were stratified as follows: WMC compared to all others (decision making, attentional control, response inhibition). Tasks were stratified in this manner given the numerous studies that used WMC as the moderator.

3. Effects by health behavior. Health behaviors included in the meta-analysis were traditional health behaviors, grouped as follows for these analyses: substances (alcohol- and smoking-related behaviors) vs. other health behaviors (diet- and sex-related behaviors). These other health behaviors were combined into a group because no separate behavior among them had a sufficient number of studies to

analyze in a more specific group. The search did not reveal other health behaviors studied in terms of the specified dual process interaction.

3. Effects by population. Analyses by age of population studied were defined here as follows: Adolescents (range in studies, mean of 13.6 to 16.7) vs. adults (range in studies, mean of 19.3 to 32.52). These analyses were considered given that adolescents are particularly vulnerable to lack of self-control and disadvantageous decision-making due to the relatively delayed maturation of the prefrontal cortex (Giedd, 2008; Gogtay, Giedd, Lusk, et al., 2004).

Statistical Analyses

In total, 18 articles with 36 analyses of moderating effects were extracted with an overall sample size of 4,743 (1,991 adults and 2,752 adolescents). Absolute values of Pearson's r were used for effect sizes in this meta-analysis. Based on guidelines provided by Lipsey and Wilson (2001), effect sizes were calculated and converted to correlation coefficients from F values, t values, degrees of freedom, Z values, or p values. For those studies reporting only beta coefficients, the missing correlation (r) coefficient was imputed following procedures outlined in Peterson and Brown (2005). The imputation approach recommended by Peterson and Brown was based on analysis of more than 1,700 corresponding beta and r coefficients extracted from published studies and was shown to be able to provide relatively accurate and precise population effect-size estimates. Some articles included results analyzed from different samples and many articles reported results on multiple moderators or multiple behavioral outcomes. Several steps recommended by Rosenthal and DiMatteo (2001) and Rosenthal and Rubin (1986) were followed to aggregate effect sizes from multiple studies. First, articles reporting analyses in different samples were treated as multiple studies with each sample equal to one study (e.g., two separate studies were included for Hofmann et al., (2009)). Second, articles reporting analyses on different construct categories of moderators (e.g. decision making or working memory capacity) or different health behaviors (e.g. alcohol use or sex behaviors) were split into multiple studies with each distinctive moderator or behavior equal to

one study. Finally, for studies reporting several analysis results relating variables under the same construct category, an aggregated effect size was calculated by averaging these correlation coefficients. The overall analysis included 27 studies that tested moderating effects of control functions on implicit processes in health behaviors. Strata were also created to examine 1) effects by moderators, 2) effects by behaviors, and 3) effects by age group.

Statistical analyses were conducted using the Comprehensive Meta Analysis Version 3 software (Biostat, Inc.). Fisher's z-transformed correlation coefficient was used for the analyses (Lipsey 2001), and the pooled coefficient and 95% CIs were then transformed back to the original scale. The heterogeneity in effect size results across studies was examined using the Q statistic (DerSimonian 1986, Hedges 2001). Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.10$ rather than 0.05, as the statistical power of the test may be low. If results of the test indicated homogeneity among studies, a fixed effects model was used for calculation of summary effect size. Otherwise, a random effects model was adopted. The fixed effects model assumes the variability between studies is exclusively due to random variation and individual studies are simply weighted by their precision. The random effects model assumes a different underlying effect for each study and takes this into consideration as an additional source of variation.

Subgroup analyses were conducted to estimate the effect size in each subgroup of studies and to compare the effect sizes within subgroups (i.e. adolescents vs. adults in age strata; sexual & eating behaviors vs. substance use in outcome behaviors strata; DM/AC/RI vs. WMC in moderators strata) under the Analysis of Variance framework of meta-analysis. Further, subgroups of substance use and working memory capacity were analyzed by age group (i.e. substance & adolescents vs. substance & adults; WMC & adolescents vs. WMC & adults). Funnel plots were generated and the degree of asymmetry for publication bias evaluated. Although we were unable to completely rule out the possibility of publication bias, recomputed summary effect sizes with imputations following Duval and Tweedie's (2000) trim and fill procedure revealed almost identical estimates from the original analysis without imputations, indicating the

effects of possible publication bias were minimal in the present analysis.

Table 1. Characteristics of Studies in Meta Analysis

Author	N	Age Group	Mean Age	Behavior	Outcome Category	Implicit Task	Moderator Task	Moderator Category	r	SE
Ames-2012	166	Adult	30	Condom use/multiple partners	Sex/Diet	WP	IGT	DM/AC/RI	.23	.08
Capelli-2015	166	Adult	30	Alcohol use	Substance	WP	IGT	DM/AC/RI	.15	.08
Christiansen-2012a	97	Adult	28.95	Alcohol use	Substance	SRC	Go/NoGo	DM/AC/RI	.14	.10
Christiansen-2012b	97	Adult	28.95	Alcohol use	Substance	SRC	DD	DM/AC/RI	.15	.10
Grenard-2008a	145	Adolescent	16.7	Alcohol use	Substance	WP	SOPT	WMC	.20	.08
Grenard-2008b	145	Adolescent	16.7	Cigarette use	Substance	WP	SOPT	WMC	.20	.08
Grenard-2012a	353	Adult	31.54	Condom use/multiple partners	Sex/Diet	WP	Ospan	WMC	.11	.05
Grenard-2012b	132	Adult	32.52	Condom use/multiple partners	Sex/Diet	WP	Ospan	WMC	.02	.09
Hofmann-2008a	117	Adult	22.38	Eating/candy consumption	Sex/Diet	SC-IAT	Span	WMC	.19	.09
Hofmann-2009a	118	Adult	23	Eating/candy consumption	Sex/Diet	SC-IAT	Span	WMC	.26	.09
Hofmann-2009b	118	Adult	23	Eating/candy consumption	Sex/Diet	Sc-IAT	SST	DM/AC/RI	.22	.09
Houben-2009	71	Adult	20.49	Alcohol use/problems	Substance	IAT	Stroop	DM/AC/RI	.28	.12
Nederkorn-2010	73	Adult	19.5	Eating/weight change	Sex/Diet	SC-IAT	SST	DM/AC/RI	.23	.12
Peeters-2012	349	Adolescent	13.6	Alcohol use	Substance	AAT	Stroop	DM/AC/RI	.15	.05
Pieters-2014a	427	Adolescent	13.96	Alcohol use	Substance	SRC	SOPT	WMC	.06	.05
Pieters-2014b	427	Adolescent	13.96	Alcohol use	Substance	VPT	SOPT	WMC	.01	.05
Pieters-2014c	427	Adolescent	13.96	Alcohol use	Substance	IAT	SOPT	WMC	.0002	.05
Pieters-2014d	427	Adolescent	13.96	Alcohol use	Substance	WP	SOPT	WMC	.01	.05
Pieters-2012	238	Adolescent	13.82	Alcohol use	Substance	SRC	SOPT	WMC	.03	.07
Salemink-2014a	81	Adult	22.7	Alcohol use/binging	Substance	WSAP/positive	Ospan	WMC	.22	.11
Salemink-2014b	81	Adult	22.7	Alcohol use/binging	Substance	WSAP/negative	Ospan	WMC	.12	.11
Sharbanee-2013	80	Adult	19.3	Alcohol use	Substance	AAT	Ospan	WMC	.11	.11
Thush-2008	81	Adolescent	16.34	Alcohol use	Substance	SC-IAT	SOPT	WMC	.28	.11
van Hemel-Ruiter- 2015	86	Adolescent	14.86	Alcohol use	Substance	VPT	ANT	DM/AC/RI	.08	.11
Wiers-2009	57	Adult	21.07	Alcohol use/aggression	Substance	IAT	Stroop	DM/AC/RI	.31	.13
Woud-2015a	92	Adult	21.2	Alcohol use	Substance	WSAP/positive	Stroop	DM/AC/RI	.01	.11
Woud-2015b	92	Adult	21.2	Alcohol use	Substance	WSAP/negative	Stroop	DM/AC/RI	.14	.10

Note: WP=Word Production; SRC=Stimulus-Response Compatibility; SC-IAT= Single Category Implicit Association Test; IAT= Implicit Association Test; AAT=Approach Avoidance Task; VPT=Visual Dot Probe; WSAP=Word Sentence Association Paradigm. DM=Decision Making; AC= Attentional Control; RI= Response Inhibition; WMC=Working Memory Capacity. Substances include cigarette use and alcohol use behaviors.

Results

Information on sample size and effect sizes (i.e. correlation coefficient and 95% confidence interval) for 27 studies on moderating effects is presented in Table 1. The correlation coefficients range from .0002 to .31 among all 27 studies. The range of correlation coefficients of moderating effects by different strata are summarized as follow: 1) from .01 to .31 for adults only, 2) from .0002 to .28 for adolescents only, 3) from .0002 to .31 among studies targeting substance use as the outcome variable, 4)

from .02 to .26 among studies targeting sex or eating behaviors as the outcome variables, 5) from .01 to .31 among studies focused on decision making, attentional control or response inhibition as the moderator, and 6) from .0002 to .28 among studies focused on working memory capacity as the moderator.

Strata	N of Studies	Fixed Effects Estimation r	Fixed Effects Estimation 95% CI	Random Effects Estimation r	Random Effects Estimation 95% CI	Heterogeneity Test Q	Heterogeneity Test df	Heterogeneity Test p
Age Groups								
Adolescents	10	0.07	.03-.10	0.08	.02-.13	16.38	9	0.059
Adults	17	0.16	.12-.20	0.16	.12-.20	11.94	16	0.748
Data Outcome Variables								
Substance Use	20	0.09	.05-.12	0.1	.06-.14	27.02	19	0.104
Substance_Adolescents	10	0.07	.03-.10	0.08	.02-.13	16.38	9	0.06
Substance_Adults	10	0.15	.09-.22	0.15	.09-.22	5.23	9	0.81
Sexual & Eating Behaviors	7	0.16	.10-.22	0.17	.10-.23	6.68	6	0.352
Moderators								
DM/AC/RI	12	0.17	.12-.22	0.17	.12-.22	6.72	11	0.821
WMC	15	0.08	.04-.11	0.09	.05-.14	23.3	14	0.06
WMC_Adolescents	8	0.05	.01-.09	0.07	.008-.13	13.52	7	0.06
WMC_Adults	7	0.14	.08-.20	0.14	.08-.20	5.08	6	0.534
Overall	27	0.1	.08-.13	0.12	.08-.16	38.45	26	0.05

Note: DM=Decision Making; AC= Attentional Control; RI= Response Inhibition; WMC=Working Memory Capacity. Substance use includes cigarette and alcohol use behaviors. Homogeneity analysis based on Fisher's r.

Pooled coefficients and 95% CI obtained from both fixed and random effects models and results of heterogeneity tests are presented in Table 2. A less than .10 p value of heterogeneity test indicates

heterogeneity among studies. As a result, pooled coefficients from the random effects model should be considered. Therefore, in our analysis, random effects estimates of pooled coefficients were used for the analysis with data from the overall studies (pooled $r=.12$, $p<.001$), and the analyses among studies targeted on adolescents only (pooled $r=.08$, $p=.004$), studies focused on WMC as moderator (pooled $r=.09$, $p<.001$), the subgroup of studies on substance use & adolescents (pooled $r=.08$, $p=.004$), and the subgroup of studies on WMC & adolescents (pooled $r=.07$, $p=.025$). Fixed effects estimations were used for the analyses in other strata (i.e. adults only, substance use behaviors, sexual or eating behaviors, moderators as DM/AC/RI, and subgroups of substance use & adults and WMC & adults) in which the pooled coefficients ranged from .09 to .17 with p values all less than .001. The range (from .08 -.17) of the absolute values of pooled correlation coefficients of moderating effects estimated from either random-effects or fixed-effects models reflected a small to close-to-medium effect size, as defined by Cohen (1988).

The subgroup analyses comparing effect size of studies within subgroups revealed significant differences in effect size between subgroups of adolescents and adults ($p=.02$), between subgroups of DM/AC/RI as moderators and working memory ($p=.04$), between subgroups of sexual and eating behaviors and substance use ($p=.03$), and between age groups within the subgroup of substance use ($p=.08$) when p -less-than-.10 criteria was applied. A clinically significant, but not statistically significant, difference in effect size was observed between age groups within the WMC subgroup ($r=.07$ for adolescents vs. $r=.14$ for adults, $p=.13$). The lack of statistical significance was likely due to the small number of studies in each age group within the WMC subgroup ($n=8$ for adolescents and $n=7$ for adults).

Figure 1. Forrest plot of study effects sizes for the various moderators (i.e. working memory capacity vs. decision making, attentional control and response inhibition). For each study, the 95% confidence interval for the point estimate/effect size is shown.

Figure 2. Forrest plot of study effects size for the outcome variables (i.e. sexual and eating behaviors vs. substance use). For each study, the 95% confidence interval for the point estimate/effect size is shown.

Figure 3. Forrest plot for the study effects size for each age group (i.e. adolescents vs. adults). For each study, the 95% confidence interval for the point estimate/effect size is shown.

Discussion

This meta-analysis evaluated a specific form of dual process interaction across a range of health behaviors. The analyses focused on studies that used indirect assessments of implicit associative processes and neurocognitive, performance measures of control functions validated across multiple lines of research. Individual differences in level of control function affects one's capability of effectively regulating, controlling or thinking through a behavior before acting. This complex interaction between control functions and associative processes involving multiple neural systems is thought to underlie many human behaviors.

Overall, 27 tested interactions involving 1,991 adults and 2,752 adolescents revealed an aggregate weighted average correlation of .12, a small, but significant effect. The nature of most significant interactions in the studies reviewed was in the form of a complete crossover for +1 and -1 standard deviation from the mean. A few studies revealed a slightly different form with no crossover but non-parallel lines at different levels of control. All studies revealed a protective or regulatory effect of moderators on implicit associative processes and related health habits. In all studies investigating risky implicit associations (e.g., that foster hazardous behavior), the significant interactions revealed that control functions dampen or block effects of implicit associations on behavior.

The results revealed variability in effect size across studies as a function of age, with adults showing stronger protective effects from moderators on health habits than adolescents. This finding is consistent with a key prospective study that evaluated developmental differences in brain regions of youth every two years, from age 4 to 21 (Gogtay et al., 2004). Gogtay and colleagues found regions implicated in reasoning and executive control functions, mediated by the prefrontal cortical regions, matured last during late adolescence (Sowell et al., 2004; Gogtay et al., 2004; Toga, Thompson & Sowell, 2006). As frontal functions are not yet fully developed, dual process approaches argue that there will be less of a counterbalance in decision and self-control abilities among younger age groups (Crews & Boettiger, 2009; Gogtay et al., 2004; Giedd et al., 2009). Alternatively, some important subcortical structures (implicated in

habit formation and reward processing, Yin & Knowlton, 2006b) have been found in imaging studies to mature earlier in life (Giedd, 2008). Early maturation of regions supporting habit and implicit associations implies that some neural regions are prepared to support the acquisition of habits by adolescence, but moderating influences may not be sufficiently developed. Given protective frontal functions are not yet fully developed, dual process approaches suggest there will be less of a counterbalance. The results here provide some preliminary support for this perspective.

Effect sizes also varied for the different moderators with decision making, attentional control and response inhibition ($r=.17$) having a stronger moderating effect than working memory capacity ($r=.09$) for the pooled studies. This finding was further explored in subgroup analyses given approximately half the studies in adults and the majority in adolescents tested interactions with working memory tasks. Since it was unclear to what extent the adolescents were attenuating the effects for working memory capacity (WMC), subgroup analyses examined moderating effects by age group. The results revealed a larger effect size for adults ($r=.14$) relative to adolescents ($r=.07$). These findings are not inconsistent with research showing that the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, implicated in WMC, is one of the last regions to be fully sculpted (Giedd et al., 2009). Further, it should be noted that different methods were used to assess WMC in adults (span tasks) and adolescents (self-ordered pointing tasks), which may have affected our findings. Effects of different methodologies require further investigation.

With respect to health behaviors, studies on diet and sexual behavior had a larger effect size than studies on substance use (alcohol and cigarette use). Although each of these behaviors are supported by both common and distinct neurobiological systems, this finding is consistent with the perspective that a rapid formation of automaticity may result from experiences from non-natural rewards like substances of abuse (Everitt & Robbins, 2005). However, the only studies on diet and sexual behaviors reviewed were in adults, whereas substance use was assessed in both adult and adolescent populations. Therefore, since it was again unclear if the effect size was attenuated by the adolescent studies on substance use, we

evaluated substance use by age group. Again, the results revealed a larger moderated effect for adults ($r=.15$) than adolescents ($r=.08$). Although tentative, these findings suggest that the countervailing influence of neurocognitive control functions (System 2) may be operating more effectively in adults in the studies examined here relative to the adolescents. This is also consistent with age-related maturation of prefrontal brain regions and concomitant function.

The specified interaction evaluated here is only one form of a dual process interaction. There have been many important contributions using alternative methods to evaluate dual processes in health and other behaviors. Many of these studies have used similar indirect tests of association, but self-report measures of behavioral control or regulation. Further, many studies have evaluated dual process interactions for behaviors that may not be construed as traditional health behaviors but demonstrate strong moderator effects. For example, Hoffman et al., (2008) found a significant moderating effect of working memory capacity on the influence of associative processes on anger expression and sexual interest behavior (erotic viewing time, also see Frieze & Hofmann, 2012). Frieze and colleagues have shown moderating effects across several behaviors with the use of self-report measures of explicit attitudes (e.g., Frieze et al., 2008; Frieze, Bargas-Avila, Hofmann & Wiers, 2010). Although these studies were not included in the present analyses, there are clearly alternative comparative analyses that could be considered between various types of dual process studies. The analyses here were constrained to only those performance tests with some multi-level support as a test of control functioning.

One area of research that appears understudied concerns preventive associations and preventive health behaviors. Only one study in this review examined preventive associations regarding health behavior (safe sex associations and condom use). This single study showed a facilitating effect of a control function on application of preventive associations to behavior (Grenard, Ames & Stacy, 2012). If the nature of this effect is replicated with other preventive associations and behaviors, it may argue that better control functions (like WMC) help people act more adaptively whether the behavior is risky or preventive, even

when associations are triggered automatically. Some control functions may help individuals override automatically activated risky impulses or more effectively engage in preventive tendencies fostered by preventive associations. Further, most of the studies conducted have involved behaviors implicated in endogenous reward systems (diet, risky sex) or engagement of such systems through non-natural means (drugs). Yet, a range of other health habits can likely become automatic with repetition without activating such systems. For example, seatbelt use, sunscreen use, medication adherence, self-exams, regular screening, and many other health behaviors can often become habitual. Future investigation of dual process interactions in these behaviors would shed more light on the generality and form of this interaction.

Limitations

One limitation of this meta-analysis is also a primary strength; that is, limiting the studies to those that tested a specific form of the interaction with somewhat common assessments. All reviewed studies used moderator methods with multiple lines of support and most with known neural correlates. Given the range of measurement strategies and limited number of certain control tasks, we had to group some control functions that may have some specific and overlapping neural systems with working memory capacity. Further, given the lack of studies for certain functions and behaviors, we were unable to evaluate differences in specific functions by age. For example, only two studies evaluated attentional control in adolescents (van Hemel-Ruiter et al., 2015; Peeters et al. 2012), and no studies looked at decision making or response inhibition in adolescents. Similarly, no studies evaluated diet and sex in adolescents. Therefore, it is difficult to make reliable inferences for some moderator effects. Finally, in general, it is difficult to detect reliable moderator effects in non-experimental studies (see McClelland & Judd, 1993). Nevertheless, this meta-analysis provides supportive evidence for the specified protective effect of several key neurocognitive control functions with respect to several health behaviors (with larger effects in adults). Further research on the specified interaction is recommended.

Conclusions

In sum, the specific dual process approach to health behavior addressed in this meta-analysis suggests that decisions to engage in a particular health-related behavior result from a synergy between an automatic associative system and an executive control system. The evidence from the meta-analysis revealed small effects to support this assertion. In its most studied form, this interaction suggests that executive control functions dampen or block effects of potentially harmful implicit associations on behavior. The studies reviewed in this meta-analysis help elucidate the interplay of associative and control process effects on health behaviors in adolescents and adults, with implications for interventions that may focus on associative and executive control processes.

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